

The Profound Contribution of Sañt Śiromaṇi Digambarācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj, a Symbol of Excellence of Knowledge and Penance

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Sañt Śiromaṇi Digambarācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj, a revered spiritual leader, a great ascetic, a philosopher, a great poet, an epitome of scholarship and spiritual insight, has left an indelible mark on the spiritual landscape through his profound teachings and exemplary life. He is also known as the Saint of Sadalaga because he was born in the village Chikkodi in Belgaum (Sadalga) district of Karnataka on *Aśvina Śukla Pūrṇimā* (*Śarada Pūrṇimā*), 10 October 1946, Vikram Samvat 2003. He had the privilege of getting the discipleship of Ācārya Śrestha Mahākavi Jñānsāgarji Mahārāj. His journey from Vidyādhara, his childhood name, to Vidyāsāgar was one of deep commitment towards acquiring and imparting knowledge. He, who was detached from worldly ostentation, has dedicated his life to the pursuit of knowledge and the dissemination of knowledge. Born into a world yearning for enlightenment, he emerged as a guiding light who led the country on the path of intellectual awakening. (Jain, 2024)

Epitome of Jain Wisdom:

One of Ācārya Vidyāsāgar Ji's most notable contributions is his relentless effort to revive and propagate the ancient Jain wisdom. In a rapidly changing world, he emphasized the timeless relevance of Jain teachings, guiding his followers on a path of self-realization and

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spiritual enlightenment. Through discourses, writings, and educational initiatives, he sought to preserve and transmit the profound knowledge embedded in the *Āgamas* (Canonical Texts).

I consider myself extremely fortunate that I, along with my father and mother, had the privilege of visiting him at many places like *Damoh, Kundalpur, Garhakota, and Jabalpur in Madhya Pradesh (Bharat)*, and got the great fortune of giving him *Āhāra Vidhi* at some places.

Ācārya Śri had a special blessing for my father Prof. Phoolchand Jain Premi, Varanasi. My father had done research work “Critical study of *Mūlācāra*” on ‘*Mūlācāra*’ – Prakrit Canonical Text of Ācārya Vattakera, which is considered an ideal research work on *Śramanācara* (code of conduct of Ascetics) in the field of research. Ācārya Śri’s whole life was based on *Mūlācāra*. With the blessings of Ācārya Śri, later on, my father and mother Dr. Munni Jain, by working on the rare ancient manuscripts found, also brought to light a scripture called *Mūlācāra Bhāshā Vacanikā*. Ācārya Śri also did sermons of this scripture in his huge *Muni Sangha*. With his inspiration, after years of research and hard work, my father wrote a well-researched work named ‘*Śramaṇa Saṁskṛti aur Vaidika Vrātya*’, which was published by Bharatiya Jnanpith, and also inaugurated by Acharya Shri.

At the heart of Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj's legacy lies his profound understanding and promotion of the Prakrit language. In an era where the world is rapidly evolving, he staunchly held onto the roots of our linguistic heritage, emphasizing the importance of preserving and promoting the rich tapestry of Prakrit literature. His tireless efforts in reviving interest in Prakrit have not only safeguarded our linguistic diversity but have also ignited a renewed passion for the beauty and depth inherent in our ancient texts.

An ideal embodiment of penance and renunciation

Saint Ācārya Muni Vidyasagar used to follow strict rules. He never consumed things like sugar, salt, green vegetables, fruits, dry fruits, oil, allopathic medicines, milk and curd in his ascetic life. These things were completely prohibited in his diet. Saint Ācārya Muni Vidyāsāgar used to take *Āhār* (pure and faultless food) once a day by making fingers of his hands (*Karpatra*) and also used to take a limited diet i.e. less than the number of *Grāsa* (mouthful intake of food) decided by him. Never ate much. He used to drink water only once a day, that too 5 anjuli before and 5 anjuli after meals. He had fixed rules not only for eating but also for sleeping. He used to sleep on one side only on a wooden bed. Neither mattress, sheet, nor mat was spread on it. Ācārya Muni Vidyasagar never took money from anyone.

Nor was any trust ever formed. He was strictly against taking money. Ācārya Muni Vidyasagar was Aniyat Vihari. He never made a travel schedule. Whenever he used to travel, no one knew in

which direction he would go. Even when the devotees asked, he never gave this information (WD, n.d.).

Literary Contributions

The Ācārya's literary oeuvre is a testament to his brilliance. His writings, characterized by their intellectual depth and spiritual resonance, have touched the hearts and minds of readers worldwide. His ability to distill complex philosophical concepts into accessible and meaningful prose has made his work a beacon for seekers of knowledge and spiritual enlightenment. His spiritual and literary genius has given to society and mankind at large rare books of Scholarly wisdom, couched in a language that even the lay and common reader can understand with ease. He is a linguist, versatile in Hindi, Prakrit, Sanskrit, Marathi, Bengali, English and other Indian languages. Some of his notable publications are as follows –

1. *Narmadā kā Narama Kaṅkara* (The Soft pebble of Narmada)
2. *Dubo Mat, Lagāo Dubakī* (Don't be drowned but Dip-dive)
3. *Totā kyon Rotā* (Why does a parrot cry?)
4. *Cetanā ke Gaharāva Mein* (In the depths of consciousness)
5. *Mukmati (Mute Clay) is the crowning glory* – his philosophical epic.

His *Mahākāvya* (The Great Epic) 'MŪKMĀTI' grouped under the various heads of marvelous topics taking into consideration the utility of the soil and its reflection on the life of mankind to mould and divert to achieve the blissful journey of life. It consists of ślokas, chhaṅd, and talented sayings and proverbs curved into lyric and poetry by the Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji. With the vivid topics more connected with life, Philosophy, Spirituality, ethics, and the National awakening of human beings, it added another link of golden chains to the great scriptures of Indian heritage and philosophy (Chhabra, 2007). 'Mook Maati' has been and is being translated into Marathi, English, Bengali, Kannada, Gujarati, Urdu, Sanskrit Languages, and Brahmi script etc. Ācārya Śri has evaluated the epic on the basis of five grounds, namely:-

1) Establishing the human values of life (2) Setting the ideals of life of the age, (3) Cooperation in cultural upliftment, (4) Advanced philosophical thoughts, and (5) Capability to produce life- giving energy (Soni, 1991). About 283 Hindi scholars have written reviews on 'Mook Maati' Mimamsa (Part 1, 2, 3), which have been published by Bharatiya Jnanpith. On this, 4 D.Litt, 50 Ph.D., 8 M.Phil., 2 M.Ed., and 6 M.A., etc. have been done (Patni, n.d.). We have amply seen that the Ācārya Śri has done justice to test this compendium of monasticism which provides a direction to the other philosophies of the world through Jain philosophy to

which Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Mahārāj is devoted and dedicated heart and soul.

With the vivid topics more connected with life, Philosophy, Spiritual, ethical, and National awakening of human beings, it added another link of golden chains to the great scriptures of Indian heritage and philosophy. He additionally contributed *hindī śataka*, *ācārya stuti saroja*, More than 500 haiku poems, Verse translation of 22 texts of Jainācāryas, 10 spiritual hymns, 9 devotional Geet, Written compositions in languages like English, Bengali, Kannada, Prakrit etc.

He has created many texts in the Sanskrit language, among which the *Śāradā Stuti*, *Pañcāstikāya kā Saṃskṛta Pratirūpaka*, *Dhīrodaya Campūkāvya*, *Saṃskṛta Śataka*, (*Śramaṇaśatakam*, *Nirañjanaśatakam*, *Bhāvanāśatakam*, *Parīśahajayaśatakam*, *Sunītiśatakam*, etc.) are prominent. Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj's contributions extend beyond the realms of literature.

‘Bade Bābā’ of Kundalpur and Visionary Ācārya Śri

Ācārya Śri was the main source of inspiration for the construction of the new main temple for the ancient idol of the first Jain Tirthankara Adinath Rishabhdeva, popularly also known as 'Bade Bābā'. According to an inscription of Vikram Samvat 1757, the former temple situated on the hill was the oldest temple of Kundalpur (District Damoh, Madhya Pradesh), in which 'Bade Baba' was seated, with the inspiration of Ācāryashree, this ancient idol has been shifted to a new grand huge temple today, whose historical *Pañcakalyanaka* had happened in 2022, witnessing the gathering of 1.5 million devotees. This beautiful temple is in Nagara architectural style and is one of the tallest Jain temples in the world, completed it only under the guidance of Ācārya Śri, who is often referred to as "Chhote Baba" in relation to the image of 'Bade Bābā'. (Sources, n.d.)

Social Welfare Initiatives

A true embodiment of selfless service, Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj actively engaged in various social welfare initiatives and humanitarian activities. He championed causes related to poverty alleviation, healthcare, education, environmental preservation, and community development. His teachings inspired countless followers to actively contribute to the well-being of society, emphasizing the importance of compassion and service to humanity.

Due to his inspiration, artificial limbs, hearing aids, crutches, and three-wheel cycles have been distributed in many handicapped camps organized by Jain Samaj. Free eye operations, medicines, and spectacles have been distributed through the camps. A free handicapped assistance centre is running in 'Sarvodaya Tīrtha' Amarkantak. In the spirit of

kindness to animals, *Dayodaya Gaushālās* have been established in various states of the

country, where thousands of animals going to slaughter are being brought and given protection. Ācārya Śri feels that the public awareness campaign to stop animal meat export should not be limited to any party, religion, or society, but there should be collective participation of all political parties, society, religious leaders, and individuals in it. (Patni, n.d.)

His social and humanitarian endeavors have left an indelible impact on society. Through educational initiatives, he has empowered countless individuals, providing them with the tools to navigate the challenges of the modern world while staying rooted in our cultural ethos. Likewise, he saw a paramount role for agriculture in our economy, also stressing making agriculture modern as well as sustainable. His work towards reforming jail inmates was also noteworthy.

Ācārya Śri always used to say that “it is the duty of all of us to support the weaker sections of the society and make them like you. One can never be made one's own self through money, but one can be taught good deeds by giving one the means to earn money. For this, this non-violent work of handloom can be considered the best work”. Some key initiatives by him are –

- **Promotion of Universal Values through Education**

Education was an area very close to his heart. It was his firm belief that education is the cornerstone of a just and enlightened society. He championed the cause of knowledge as a means to empower individuals, enabling them to lead lives of purpose and contribution. Ācārya Vidyasagar wanted our youngsters to get an education that is rooted in our cultural ethos. He also believed that a holistic education is one that focuses on skilling and innovating. He took immense pride in India's linguistic diversity and encouraged youngsters to learn Indian languages. (Modi, 2024)

Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj advocated for universal values that transcend cultural and religious boundaries. His teachings emphasized the core principles of love, compassion, tolerance, and selflessness. He always used to say – '*carāṇa nahīn, ācarāṇa chuo*' (Touch the conduct, not the feet). By promoting these values, he aimed to foster harmony and understanding among people of diverse backgrounds, fostering a sense of global unity and interconnectedness.

- **Who raised the voice of calling 'Bhārat' as 'Bhārat'**

Ācārya Śri's slogan was '*India nahin, Bhārat bolo*'. He had been saying in his sermons that Bharat should be called Bharat. He had even been running a nationwide campaign since

2017.

He said that since ancient times, our country has been known as *Vishwaguru* by the name of Bhāratvarsha. But after independence from 200 years of British slavery, the name of the country was changed to India in English. The ancient history of the country should not be forgotten, hence the original authentic name of the country, Bharat, should be recognized. (Upadhyay, 2019)

● **Educational Reforms and Promoting Girl Education :**

Recognizing the pivotal role of education in shaping individuals and societies, Ācārya Vidyāsāgar Ji spearheaded educational reforms rooted in spiritual principles. He believed in an education system that not only imparts academic knowledge but also nurtures moral and ethical values. His efforts led to the establishment of educational institutions that aimed at holistic development, fostering a harmonious blend of academic excellence and character-building.

Pratibha Sthali is a unique and unique girls' residential educational institution across India, which has blossomed and flourished due to the immense grace and vision of Maharaj Ji. On 18 February 2004, the foundation stone of Pratibhasthali was laid in the presence of Ācārya Śri 108 Vidyāsāgar ji Maharaj Chaturvidh Sangh at Tilwara Ghat on the holy banks of the holy river Narmada in Jabalpur. Today, along with Jabalpur, branches of Pratibha Sthali in Dongargarh (Chhattisgarh), Ramtek (Maharashtra), Indore (Madhya Pradesh), Lalitpur (Uttar Pradesh) are also smoothly engaged in propagating Vidya. Here education is not a means of earning money but is a sacred process of imparting knowledge. Here, Bal Brahmacharini Vidushi and trained teachers are providing their selfless services to build a bright future for the girls. This C.B.S.E. recognized institute is reviving the memory of ancient Gurukuls in today's modern environment. "The aim of education here is not to sustain life but to build it." (Sthali, n.d.)

Building a *Svāvalambī* (self-reliant) *Bhārata* through *Hathkarghā*

He believed that since ancient times, India has been the world's largest textile production centre due to its textile manufacturing art, but in this era of mechanization, we have hurt handicrafts a lot. As a result, rural areas, which are called the soul of India, are today facing serious problems like unemployment, poverty, and migration. To solve many such problems, with the blessings of His Holiness Ācārya Guruvar Śri 108 Vidyasagarji Maharaj, many handloom training and production centres are being operated across India. Under the blessings of Ācārya Pravar, 'Chal Charkha Women Training and Employment Centres' are being operated at 9 places in different states of India like Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh,

Maharashtra, Uttar

Pradesh, and Himachal Pradesh. Tihar Jail signed an MoU with Chal Charkha, Pratibhamandal Trust. This organization will provide skill training in the field of handloom and handicrafts to the women prisoners in jails and will also provide employment to these women prisoners after their release. (Vidyapeetha, n.d.)

Golden Memories

I remember in March 2020, I reached Pratibha Sthali, Jabalpur early in the morning with my wife Smt. Neha Jain to have his darshan. He was doing *Swādhyāya*, I went near him, touched his feet, and introduced myself to him. He was very happy to know that I am the son of 'Premiji' and am working in the field of Jain philosophy to continue the legacy. With his familiar smile, he also asked about my father Prof. Phoolchand Jain Premi, mother Dr. Munni Jain, elder brother Dr. Anekant Jain, and elder sister Dr. Indu. It was surprising to know that he was speaking everyone's name. He also asked me about my research topic 'Contribution of Ācārya Kundkund in the development of philosophical and spiritual thinking' and also happily blessed me. I wanted to capture that moment in my eyes. Even today, when I close my eyes and remember him, this golden scene comes to my mind. (Jain, 2024)

Heartfelt Tribute

Ācārya Śri was a great ascetic who observed 36 'Basic Gunas' in his philosophy of life. During today's *Pañcam Kāla* (Fifth Ara), his Routine duties were like that of the *Caturtha Kāla* (fourth Ara). Enduring health-related *parishaha's* (hardships) with equanimity, Ācārya Śri gave up the title of *Ācāryatva* and accepted full *Sallekhanā* (Voluntary Ritualized death). He had completely given up the *Caturvidha Āhār* (fourfold diet) three days earlier and then on 18th February 2024, at the age of 77, he attained Samadhi-Marana at Chandragiri Tirtha in Dongargarh (Chhattisgarh, Bharat) and merged into the Panchatatva. If we analyze his 'Municharya' carefully, it becomes clear that his 'Sallekhana' had been going on for many years.

As we pay tribute to Ācārya Śri Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj, let us reflect on the profound influence he has had on our nation and the literary world. His legacy is not confined to the pages of history but lives on in the hearts of those who have been touched by his wisdom and benevolence. He embodies the Jain ideal of universal welfare (*lokasaṅgraha*) by his humanitarian outreach to all beings. His life and teachings continue to inspire and guide millions on their spiritual journey. His contributions to reviving Jain wisdom, promoting universal values, initiating educational reforms, engaging in social welfare, and fostering interfaith dialogue have left an indelible impact on society. As we reflect on the legacy of this

revered Ācārya, may we draw inspiration from his teachings to create a more harmonious and compassionate world.

Ācārya Vidyāsāgar Ji Munimahārāj, a true luminary, has lit the way for generations to come. May his teachings continue to guide us, and may his spirit inspire the pursuit of knowledge, wisdom, and compassion in the years to come.

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